

EVOLUTIONS OF WOMEN AND GENDER IN NIGERIA AND THE IMPACT ON NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This research assessed the evolution of women and gender in Nigeria and the impact of women in the development of Nigeria across different sectors of the nation's economy. This work focused on secondary data through content analysis of published works. Efforts made by international organization like the United Nations Assembly toward gender equity were analysed. The evolution of women and gender in Nigeria was analysed from the pre-colonization era through colonization era to the post-colonization era. The impact of women in the development of Nigeria were analysed by the researcher in education, politics, banking, sports, agriculture and healthcare. Findings showed that women are playing great roles in the development of the nation's economy. In the banking sector, women are playing leading roles in the key sector of Nigeria's financial management. Women should be given more room to be involve indecision making from the grassroot to the government in order for the nation to tap into the wealth of capabilities embedded in the women gender.

KEYWORDS: Women, Gender, National development and Equity

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of women and gender roles in Nigeria is a crucial aspect of the country's societal development. Understanding the historical trajectory and contemporary challenges faced by women is essential for assessing their impact on national progress. This presentation explores the transformation of women's roles, the advancement of gender equality, and the implications for Nigeria's socio-economic landscape. Women constitute a good percentage of rural communities in Nigeria. Akpan (2015) posits that the rural economies in developing and underdeveloped countries are characterized by enormous informal activities that are dominated by women. He further stated that women in rural areas are involved in several productive activities yet their roles are never reflected in the mainstream public development agenda. The sustainable development of any country depends on the full and equal participation of women and men (Alam, 2010; Peters, Wilson

and Bassey, 2020).

Women constitute an indispensable force in the quest for the national development of any nation, and this is visible in developed nations where gender barriers are less effective (Asaju and Adagba, 2013). The sustainable development of the country depends on the full and equal participation of women and men, and the overall development of a country depends upon the maximum utilization of her people, both men and women (Alam, 2010; Peters, Wilson and Bassey, 2020). Women's empowerment can be considered an important indicator of the socioeconomic development of any nation. According to Sharma (2016), women play important and varied roles from home to society to the workplace as a homemaker, societal well-being, and job providers and job seekers respectively. Fortunate African women who enjoyed good education have proven their abilities in several walks of life (Benjamin, 2008). They are found among successful doctors, teachers, and lawyers, and are found in industry, commerce, and public administration. These sets of women have proved the case for women's education by demonstrating their usefulness outside the home (Benjamin, 2008). Sharma (2016) posits that women are the visible backbone of any civilized society in the role of friend, daughter, daughter-in-law, sister, wife, mother, or a role of working woman, women have facilitated this male-dominant society in every aspect, and constitute approximately 50% of the World's population.

Globally, the potential of women has not been fully deployed for the development of societies due to gender-biased issues which are mostly role-specific. The majority of countries and regions of the world have more females than males, and if the population of China and India is excluded from the total population figure, there are more females than males in the rest of the world (UN, 2021). The population of females in the world is estimated at 3,904,727,342 or 3.905 billion, representing 49.58% of the world population (UN, 2021). The population of women in the world signifies a great percentage of the workforce and development agents and proper integration into development projects will bring about the achievement of development at all levels of society. Women constitute half of the world's population (Babacan, 2022).

Women's roles in development call for greater attention to women in development policy and practice and emphasize the need to integrate women into the development process (Reeves and Baden, 2000). There has been a strong emphasis on women's role in development in the 21st century the International Conference on Population and Development in 1992, the World Summit for Social Development, and the 4th World Conference on Women in 1995 (Gampaha, Ratmarana, and Kotte, 2001).

According to Akanji and Awe (2018), the role of women or men is a function of the ways that different policy regimes have either reinforced gender or deliberately reduced them through one or more of these approaches.

- Women in Development (WID): focused on welfare packages for women
 - Women and Development (WAD): AKA Add women and stir. Focused on special programs outside the mainstream.
 - Gender and Development (GAD): Based on equity and efficiency
- (Akanji and Awe, 2018)

EFFORT MADE BY INTERNATIONAL BODIES TOWARD GENDER EQUITY

- Consequently, various approaches have evolved since the advent of the 1948 Universal Declaration on Human Rights (Assembly, U. G. 1948).
- In 1975 the UN organized a World conference in Mexico to advance women's rights around the world. This gave rise to the era generally known as the Decade of Women from 1975-1985 (Fraser, 2019).
- Besides these global women's initiatives, there were also local agitations within countries in favor of equity and equality for women and this advocacy has continued till today.
- The UN General Assembly of 1984 came up with 30 articles that were set to bring gender equity, and women's roles into the development. These are;

Article 1

All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood.

Article 2

Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms outlined in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or another opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or another status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made based on the political, jurisdictional, or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it be independent, trust, non-self-governing, or under any other limitation of sovereignty.

Article 3

Everyone has the right to life, liberty, and security of person.

Article 4

No one shall be held in slavery or servitude; slavery and the slave trade shall be prohibited in all their forms.

Article 5

No one shall be subjected to torture or cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment or punishment.

Article 6

Everyone has the right to recognition everywhere as a person before the law.

Article 7

All are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law. All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this Declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination.

Article 8

Everyone has the right to an effective remedy by the competent national tribunals for acts violating the fundamental rights granted him by the constitution or by law.

Article 9

No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention, or exile.

Article 10

Everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him.

Article 11

1. Everyone charged with a penal offence has the right to be presumed innocent until proven guilty according to the law in a public trial at which he has had all the guarantees necessary for his defence.
2. No one shall be held guilty of any penal offence on account of any act or omission which did not constitute a penal offence, under national or international law, at the time when it was committed. Nor shall a heavier penalty be imposed than the one that was applicable at the time the penal offence was committed.

Article 12

No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honour and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks.

Article 13

1. Everyone has the right to freedom of movement and residence within the borders of each state.
2. Everyone has the right to leave any country, including his own, and to return to his country.

Article 14

1. Everyone has the right to seek and enjoy in other countries asylum from persecution.
2. This right may not be invoked in the case of prosecutions genuinely arising from non-political crimes or acts contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations.

Article 15

1. Everyone has the right to a nationality.
2. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his nationality nor denied the right to change his nationality.

Article 16

1. Men and women of full age, without any limitation due to race, nationality or religion, have the right to marry and to found a family. They are entitled to equal rights as to marriage, during marriage and at its dissolution.
2. Marriage shall be entered into only with the free and full consent of the intending spouses.
3. The family is the natural and fundamental group unit of society and is entitled to protection by society and the State.

Article 17

1. Everyone has the right to own property alone as well as in association with others.
2. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of his property.

Article 18

Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience, and religion; this right includes freedom to change his religion or belief, and freedom, either alone or in community with others and in public or private, to manifest his religion or belief in teaching, practice, worship, and observance.

Article 19

Everyone has the right to freedom of opinion and expression; this right includes freedom to hold opinions without interference and to seek, receive, and impart information and ideas through any media regardless of frontiers.

Article 20

1. Everyone has the right to freedom of peaceful assembly and association.
2. No one may be compelled to belong to an association.

Article 21

1. Everyone has the right to take part in the government of his country, directly or through freely chosen representatives.
2. Everyone has the right to equal access to public service in his country.
3. The will of the people shall be the basis of the authority of government; this will shall be expressed in periodic and genuine elections which shall be by universal and equal suffrage and shall be held by secret vote or by equivalent free voting procedures.

Article 22

Everyone, as a member of society, has the right to social security and is entitled to realization, through national effort and international cooperation and by the organization and resources of each State, of the economic, social, and cultural rights indispensable for his dignity and the free development of his personality.

Article 23

1. Everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favourable conditions of work, and protection against unemployment.
2. Everyone, without any discrimination, has the right to equal pay for equal work.
3. Everyone who works has the right to just and favourable remuneration ensuring for himself and his family an existence worthy of human dignity, and supplemented, if necessary, by other means of social protection.
4. Everyone has the right to form and to join trade unions for the protection of his interests.

Article 24

Everyone has the right to rest and leisure, including reasonable limitation of working hours and periodic holidays with pay.

Article 25

1. Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and his family, including food, clothing, housing medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control.
2. Motherhood and childhood are entitled to special care and assistance. All children, whether born in or out of wedlock, shall enjoy the same social protection.

Article 26

1. Everyone has the right to education. Education shall be free, at least in the elementary and fundamental stages. Elementary education shall be compulsory. Technical and professional education shall be made generally available and higher education shall be equally accessible to all based on merit.
2. Education shall be directed to the full development of the human personality and the strengthening of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. It shall promote understanding, tolerance, and friendship among all nations, racial or religious groups, and shall further the activities of the United Nations for the maintenance of peace.
3. Parents have a prior right to choose the kind of education that shall be given to their

children.

Article 27

1. Everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts, and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits.
2. Everyone has the right to the protection of the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary, or artistic production of which he is the author.

Article 28

Everyone is entitled to a social and international order in which the rights and freedoms outlined in this Declaration can be fully realized.

Article 29

1. Everyone has duties to the community in which alone the free and full development of his personality is possible.
2. In the exercise of his rights and freedoms, everyone shall be subject only to such limitations as are determined by law solely to secure due recognition and respect for the rights and freedoms of others and to meet the just requirements of morality, public order, and the general welfare in a democratic society.
3. These rights and freedoms may in no case be exercised contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations.

Article 30

Nothing in this Declaration may be interpreted as implying for any State, group or person any right to engage in any activity or to perform any act aimed at the destruction of any of the rights and freedoms set forth herein.

(UN, 1948)

EVOLUTION OF WOMEN AND GENDER IN NIGERIA

Over the last 64 years, the role of women in Nigeria's development has been determined by the disposition of the various policy regimes toward gender differences. Consequently, the history of women and gender in Nigeria has been quite unstable as the policy regime and the impact on national development have yielded varying degrees of success as well as development outcomes (Akanji and Awe, 2018).

Pre-Colonial Era

Although women played an active role in agriculture, their roles were restricted to just planting, harvesting, processing of finished products, and sales of produce as the ownership of land was an exclusive right of men in many cultures within Nigeria. However, women's contribution to the dietary staple of the family and national economy was significant and fundamental (Nnamani, 2010).

Colonial Era (1914-1960)

European Colonial administrators and missionaries introduced patriarchy into the Nigerian society which emphasized the role of women as homemakers. This Eurocentric view and cultural diffusion essentially excluded women from full participation in Nigeria's national development (Pereira, 2005). While men dominated the cultivation of cash crops for the international market, women were confined to growing food crops at the subsistent level. Colonialism promoted a social system of inequality and oppressive forms of social stratification which gave rise to a series of women's protests, notable mention is Margret Ekpo who fought against this (Ukpokolo, 2020).

Post-Colonial Era (1960-1990s)

In the wake of the independence of Nigeria and the end of the Civil War, Nigerian women began to play a significant role in national development as gender roles began to change; women became heads of households, taking up farming responsibilities as well as family income. This modest women's contribution to national development termed as *refeminization of agriculture* was marred by the era of the oil boom which shifted government interest from agriculture to oil exploration (Akanji and Awe, 2018). However, gender inequality persisted but Women's education and political participation increased paving the way for the future generation (Peters, Bassey and Usoro, 2020).

Contemporary era 2000s

Women have continued to face challenges in contemporary Nigeria, however, there have been positive developments in political participation and leadership, increased advocacy and activism; improved access to education and economic opportunities; paradigm shifts in gender roles and equality with significant change in societal norms and values (Makama, 2013).

Impact on National Development

Women in Nigeria contribute significantly to the economy, both in formal and informal sectors. They play pivotal roles in agriculture, trade, and small-scale enterprises, contributing to household income and national GDP unfortunately, much of these contributions have not been valued in monetary terms. Despite their economic contributions, women face barriers such as limited access to financial services, discriminatory practices in the workplace, and unequal pay, hindering their full economic potential (Asaju and Adagba, 2013; Peters and Bassey, 2019).

Sport

Nigerian women have made significant strides in sports, breaking barriers and achieving remarkable success in various fields. Their accomplishment not only inspires a new generation of young athletes but also contributes to national development. Successful female athletes inspire sponsorships and investment in sports infrastructure, creating jobs and stimulating local economies (Efebeh, 2020). The likes of Asisat Oshoala former Barcelona feminine player and Africa's best female player. Punch Nigeria in 2023 gave a brief detail of Nigerian women who have contributed to the development of Nigeria in sport. This list is as follows:

Tobi Amusan

Tobi Amusan's speciality is 100 metres as a track and field athlete. In 2022, she became the first-ever Nigerian world champion and world record holder in the World Athletics Championships when she won the 100m hurdles gold medal, setting the current world record of 12.12 seconds in the semi-final, followed up by a wind-assisted 12.06 s in the final. The record of the Ijebu-Ode indigene became motivation and inspiration for many, while she received commendation across the globe for her brilliant performance.

Favour Ofili

Favour Ofili, a 20-year-old Nigerian athlete, has represented the country in several local and international sports events. She won her first individual medal after racing to silver in the final of the women's 200m at the 2022 Commonwealth Games in Birmingham. In the race, Ofili clocked a time of 22.51s, putting some daylight between her and Namibia's

Christine Mboma who was trailing at full speed, trying to close the gap on her African rival. She is a Commonwealth Games winner, and All-African Games silver medalist and has also emerged top eight at the World Championships.

Asisat Oshoala

Oshoala is a Nigerian female footballer who broke into the limelight when she became the Most Valuable Player and top scorer in the 2014 Women's U-20 World Cup, as Nigeria finished runners-up to Germany. In 2015, Oshoala was named the BBC Women's Footballer of the Year. Oshoala plays for the Super Falcons of Nigeria and as a striker for FC Barcelona Feminine in Spain. She is described as one of the greatest African female footballers of all time and one of the best in the world. Oshoala has a record of winning the African Women's Footballer of the Year five times.

Mary Osijo

Osijo is also one of the outstanding athletes Nigeria has produced in recent times. A weightlifter, Osijo competed in the 87 kg category and represented Nigeria at international competitions. In August 2022, she won bronze at the 2022 Commonwealth Games. Osijo clinched the bronze medal in the Women's 87 kg Weightlifting event, lifting a combined total weight of 225 kg from Snatch, Clean, and Jerk. Osijo had an unblemished series, lifting all attempts she made in both categories and deservedly won the Bronze medal. The 25-year-old represented Nigeria at the 2014 All African Games Trial and won gold. She also won a gold and two silver at the Edo State Sports Festival in 2020.

Chiamaka Nnadozie

Nnadozie is a Nigerian footballer who plays as a goalkeeper for Paris FC in the French Division 1 Féminine and the Nigeria national team. At age 19, Nnadozie was named to the Super Falcons to compete at the 2019 FIFA Women's World Cup in France. As Nigeria's starting goalkeeper in the team's 2–0 victory over Korea, Nnadozie became the youngest goalkeeper to keep a clean sheet at the World Cup. Nnadozie was nominated for the 2021/2022 UNFP trophy of the best goalkeeper award in the D1 Arkema league.

Desire Oparanozie

Desire Oparanozie is a Nigerian footballer who plays as a forward in the Chinese Women's Super League for Wuhan Jiangnan University and the Nigerian national team with many years of experience. The Super Falcons player is popular for her fast pace and strong physique which have propelled her to become a great striker. She has been a regular member of the Nigerian national team since 2010, participating in the FIFA Women's World Cup tournaments of 2011, 2015, and 2019. She has also participated in the African Women's Championship of 2010 and 2014, 2016 and 2018, winning all four tournaments. She scored crucial goals in both the 2014 and 2016 finals.

Odunayo Adekuoroye

Adekuoroye is a Nigerian wrestler who competed in the women's freestyle 53 kg event at the 2014 Commonwealth Games where she won a gold medal. She also won a bronze medal in the 2015 World Wrestling Championships. The 28-year-old Ondo-born wrestler claimed her third successive Commonwealth Games gold in 2022 at the 2022 Commonwealth Games in Birmingham. She won the prestigious medal at the Commonwealth Games in 2014 and 2018.

Politics

Nigeria has a rich history of women breaking out of the mould to participate in politics

notwithstanding the above postulation. In their reporting Orokpo *et. al*, (2017) further opined that our pre-colonial history is replete with the exploits of Queen Amina of Zauzzau (Modern Zaria), who led armies to drive out invaders from Zaria; and Moremi of Ile-Ife, whose sacrifice for her people speaks to selfless leadership that we are so bereft of these days. Our recent past speaks of prominent women leaders like Funmilayo Ransome Kuti, a crusader, and challenger of despotic leaders, who led Egba women on a protest against taxation; Margaret Ekpo, a prominent civil rights activist; and Hajia Gambo Sawaba, who championed the cause of the oppressed in northern Nigeria. Also, Iyalode Tinubu of Lagos exemplifies the rich participation of women on the economic scene. The legacies of these women are at risk of extinction. Even though an increasing number of women are finding their way into boardrooms and providing leadership for blue-chip companies, the majority of women in Nigeria only minimally participate in economic development or politics (Orokpo, *et. al*, 2017).

Equitable participation of women in politics and government is essential to building and sustaining democracy. Comprising over 50% of the world's population, women continue to be under-represented as voters, political leaders, and elected officials. Democracy cannot truly deliver for all of its citizens if half of the population remains underrepresented in the political arena (Uki and Fiemotongha, 2020). Despite the effort being made by our countries in Africa to bridge the gap between men and women in politics, the Nigerian government has not deemed it necessary to implement this. According to Orokpo *et al*, (2017), the government of Nigeria must as a matter of priority commit resources and make a deliberate commitment towards women's empowerment, development, and better integration into the mainstream political system above all, women must get up and fight, participate and even get their due through and on merit and not just mere 30% concession as canvassed for at the 1995 Beijing conference in China.

Political representation of women in Nigeria has improved with affirmative action policies and advocacy efforts. Notable examples include Senator Oluremi Tinubu and former Speaker of the House of Representatives, Hon. Patricia Etteh. Women in leadership positions have made good policies that foster the growth of the nation (Asaju and Adagba, 2013). However, women continue to be underrepresented in political leadership positions at local, state, and federal levels, highlighting the need for sustained efforts to address structural barriers and promote inclusive governance (Nwabunkeonye, 2014).

Finance

Between 2003 to 2015 Dr. Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala brought up policies that helped reposition the financial sector of the country through the following;

- Improved Nigeria's macroeconomic stability and debt management
- She introduced the Medium Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF), thus, enhancing fiscal discipline in the nation's budgeting process
- Public financial management and promoting investment in critical sectors like agriculture, manufacturing, etc. (Okonjo-Iweala, 2007)

Vanguard Nigeria of March 2024 provided us with brief details of Nigerian women who have

done well in the banking industry in Nigeria. These include:

Tomi Somefun – Unity Bank

Tomi Somefun has assumed the role of the MD/CEO of Unity Bank Plc since August 2015. She is a fellow of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN). She holds a Bachelor of Education in English Language in 1981 from the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife. She is also an alumnus of Harvard Business School and the University of Columbia Business School, New York, USA. With a deep understanding of over 35 years of post-qualification experience, 26 of which were in the banking sector spanning key segments such as treasury and investment banking, corporate banking, rural banking, and financial inclusion, Somefun is passionate about promoting financial literacy and economic empowerment across Nigeria.

Kafilat Araoye – Lotus Bank

Kafilat Araoye emerged as the MD/CEO of Lotus Bank in 2020. She holds a first degree in History from the University of Ife, now Obafemi Awolowo University in 1985, and an M.Sc. in Industrial Relations & Personnel Management from the University of Lagos in 1987. She has attended various executive management courses at the Cranfield School of Management (UK), Lagos Business School, Institute of Management Development (Switzerland) INSEAD (France), Ross Business School, and University of Michigan (USA). Araoye started her career in 1988 at National Oil and Chemicals Marketing Company Plc (now Conoil Nigeria Plc), and moved in 1990 to Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, as the pioneer head of Human Resources. Having put over 30 years into banking, Araoye has expertise in virtually all areas of core banking, with emphasis on international and domestic operations; Business Development, Risk Management, Human Resources and Strategy, ethical banking, and social responsibility which she uses in championing her roles at Lotus Bank.

Dr Adaora Umeoji – Zenith Bank

Dr Adaora Umeoji has been appointed as the new GMD/CEO of Zenith Bank according to a statement filed with the Nigerian Exchange Limited on Tuesday, 19 March 2024. Before this appointment, Umeoji was the Deputy Managing Director of the bank since October 28, 2016, and with nearly 30 years of banking experience of which 26 years has been with Zenith Bank. Umeoji is an alumnus of Harvard Business School, where she attended the Advanced Management Programme. She is an alumnus of Columbia Business School with a Certificate in the Global Banking Program. She holds a bachelor's degree in Sociology from the University of Jos, a Bachelor's degree in accounting, and a first-class honours degree in law from Baze University, Abuja. She holds a Master of Laws from the University of Salford, United Kingdom, a Master in Business Administration from the University of Calabar, and also has a doctorate in business administration from Apollos University, USA. Umeoji also holds a Certificate in Economics for Business from the prestigious MIT Sloan School of Management, USA, and has attended various management programmes in renowned Universities around the world including the strategic thinking and Management programme at Wharton Business School, USA. Umeoji boasts of close to 30 years of cognate banking experience of which 26 years have been with the Zenith Bank, to thrust the bank further into strategic innovations.

Ireti Samuel-Ogbu – CitiBank

Ireti Samuel-Ogbu was named the MD/CEO of CitiBank in September 2020. She became the first female CEO of the bank in Nigeria. Before her appointment in 2020, she was the Europe, Middle East and Africa (EMEA) Head, of Payments and Receivables, Treasury and Trade Solutions (TTS) under Citi's Institutional Clients Group (ICG) based in London, the United Kingdom. She holds a Bachelor of Arts in Accounting and Finance from Middlesex University, UK, and an MBA from the University of Bradford, UK. Samuel-Ogbu has vast experience in international banking, bringing a global perspective to the Nigerian market, as she has served the banking needs at local and global since 1984, focussing her leadership on providing innovative financial solutions and leveraging technology to enhance customer experience.

Bukola Smith – FSDH Merchant Bank

Bukola Smith became the Managing Director/Chief Executive Officer of First Securities Discount House (Limited) Merchant Bank in April 2021. Smith holds an MBA from Alliance Manchester Business School, University of Manchester, UK, and a B.Sc. Economics from the University of Lagos. She is a Fellow of the Institute of Chartered Accounts of Nigeria (ICAN), an Honourary Member of the Chartered Institute of Bankers, and an Associate Member, of the Certified Institute of Pensions (Nigeria). Before she was appointed Managing Director, she was the Executive Director, of Business Development at First City Monument Bank and held several other leadership positions since joining in 2006. She was responsible for the banks' over 200 branches across the country, with her leadership roles and contributions in the Public Sector, Business Banking, Agriculture, and Transaction Banking Divisions. Smith brings nearly 30 years of progressive experience in the banking industry with a track record of strategic execution and leadership, including investment banking and financial structuring that are instrumental in FSDH's growth and success. She is an advocate for women in finance and actively mentors aspiring female leaders.

Miriam Olusanya – GTBank

Miriam Olusanya assumed the office of the Managing Director of Guaranty Trust Bank, in July 2021 becoming the first woman to lead the bank in that position. She is a graduate of Pharmacy from the University of Ibadan and a Master of Business Administration (majoring in finance and accounting) from the University of Liverpool, UK. Olusanya joined GTB as an executive trainee in 1998. Until she was appointed MD, she was an executive director at the bank. She is the first female MD in the bank's history. She holds a bachelor's degree in Pharmacy from the University of Ibadan and a Master of Business Administration (MBA), majoring in finance and accounting, from the University of Liverpool. Olusanya is a seasoned banker with 26 years of stellar experience, Olusanya is known for her strong leadership, strategic vision, and commitment to financial inclusion.

Nneka Onyeali-Ikpe – Fidelity Bank

Dr Nneka Onyeali-Ikpe became the GMD/CEO of Fidelity Bank Plc in January 2021, becoming the first female to assume the position in the bank's history. Nneka Onyeali-Ikpe holds a Bachelor of Law from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, and a Master of Law from Kings College, London. She has attended executive training programs at various institutions

including Harvard Business School, The Wharton School University of Pennsylvania, and London Business School, among other prestigious educational institutions. She holds an honorary doctorate in Business Administration from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN).

Onyeali-Ikpe began working in the banking industry as a legal officer for the now-defunct African Continental Bank in 1990 and subsequently worked as a treasury officer for the First African Trust Bank. She later joined Zenith Bank and Standard Chartered Bank respectively.

She joined Fidelity Bank as an executive director in January 2015 and has been passionate about innovation and technology spearheading initiatives such as PayGate Plus, an online payment platform, and the Fidelity International Trade & Creative Connect (FITCC) aimed at supporting Small and Medium Enterprise. Under her leadership, Fidelity Bank has continued to witness significant growth, increasing its Profit Before Tax (PBT) from N25.22bn in FY 2021 to N122bn in FY 2023.

Yemisi Edun – FCMB

Yemisi Edun was appointed the MD/CEO of First City Monument Bank in July 2021, and the first female to ever hold the position. Edun graduated with a bachelor's degree in Chemistry from the University of Ife (now Obafemi Awolowo University). She proceeded to the University of Liverpool, where she graduated with a master's degree in international accounting and finance.

Before she was appointed Managing Director, she was the chief financial officer of the bank and the acting chief executive officer. Edun is a fellow of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria and a CFA holder. She is also an associate member of the Chartered Institute of Stock Brokers, an Associate Member of the Chartered Institute of Taxation of Nigeria, and a member of the Information Systems Audit and Control. Edun has sterling years of banking experience with an impressive track record in risk management and corporate governance. She is also the first woman to lead the financial institution FCMB. Under her leadership, FCMB has witnessed significant growth and diversification, solidifying its position as a leading player in the Nigerian banking sector.

Halima Buba – SunTrust Bank

Halima Buba is a businesswoman and astute female banker, who also became the MD/CEO of Sun Trust Bank in January 2021 after serving as the deputy general manager of Ecobank Nigeria. Buba graduated with a Bachelor's degree in Business Management and an MBA from the University of Maiduguri. She is an alumnus of the Lagos Business School an Honourary member of the Chartered Institute of Bankers and a Fellow of the Institute of Management Consultants. She has a passion for entrepreneurship and SME development shines through in her work at SunTrust Bank. She champions financial support for small businesses 'SME Flash', recognising their crucial role in driving Nigeria's economic growth.

Yetunde Oni – Union Bank

Yetunde Oni was appointed as the first female MD/CEO of Union Bank in January 2024. She holds a degree in Economics from the University of Ibadan, Executive Training at

Oxford University, and an MBA in Business Administration from Bangor University. Before her recent appointment at the Union Bank, Oni was also the MD/CEO of the Standard Chartered Bank, Sierra Leone, from January 2021, spearheading leadership, strategy setting, and performance management. Her appointment by the Central Bank of Nigeria as the Union Bank's CEO marked a significant development in the bank's leadership, merging her extensive experience with quality qualifications to play a crucial role in the bank's strategic direction.

Agriculture

Women are crucial in agriculture and responsible for food security and sustenance. They constitute about 60% of small-scale farmers, producing crops like maize, cassava, and yams for local consumption (Oluwasola and Solomon 2019). Women are known to be the key players in rural or community development through involvement in agriculture. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), women make essential contributions to the agricultural and rural economies in all developing countries, and their roles vary considerably between and within regions and are changing rapidly in many parts of the world, where economic and social forces are transforming the agricultural sector. Rural women often manage complex households and pursue multiple livelihood strategies, making their activities typical to include producing crops, tending animals, processing and preparing food, working for wages in agricultural or other rural enterprises, collecting fuel and water, engaging in trade and marketing, caring for family members and maintaining their homes (FAO, 2011).

The participation of women in development programmes like agriculture and other forms of developmental activities has been well documented in the last two decades in the developed world. Still, in developing countries, however, such studies are very scanty and fragmented as the roles of women in development efforts are hardly acknowledged (Osirike and Egbayabo, 2012). Asaju and Adagba, (2013) observed that in the food processing and cottage industries in three Zaria villages, 90 per cent of the women were involved in at least one food processing activity or the other. United Nations report reveals that 60 – 90 per cent of the agricultural labour forces are women and they produce two-thirds of the food crops (Asaju and Adagba, 2013) Hassan and Silong (2008) posit that women have long been the mainstay of national development right from the community level and are heavily involved in community initiatives in various forms.

Education

Ekong (2006) posits that women are the real engine driving the economy of this country and are the keys to development and therefore crucial to the goal of sustainable development. Educated women are found in every part of the nation's economy, from the small scale to larger scale production and other parts of the economy. Samuel (2019) confirmed this assertion by concluding that women are the operators of the economy and constitute a major arm of the labour force and that Nigerian women are dynamic, industrious, and resourceful. The contributions of women in National Development were beyond agriculture and household duties. Some research works assessed their contributions beyond farm and household chores (subsistence) and noted that the narrow perception of women's duties may be attributed to the late arrival of women in the colonial system or administrative work due to the roles or impact

of education. According to Ekong (2008), the willingness, enthusiasm, and ability of women to actively participate in Nation building are often conditioned by many factors which are mostly social and educational.

According to Akubuilo and Omeje (2012), the introduction of Western education in Nigeria dates back to pre-colonial years and was done by the missionaries. According to Olujuwon (2011), formal education in Nigeria was under the control of Christian Missionaries between 1842 and 1881. St Andrew's College Oyo, Hope Waddel Institute Calabar, and the Baptist Training Centre Ogbomoso were among the first set of schools set up to train female teachers. These institutions provided the much-needed leadership in the production of Primary school teachers in Nigeria.

Women's education has significantly contributed to economic growth in Nigeria in several ways, some of which are:

- Increase labor force participation
- Entrepreneurship
- Reduced poverty
- Reduced gender inequality

(Adeleke *et al.*, 2024).

Women have made significant contributions to education (Peters, Basseyy and Usoro, 2020), with many serving as teachers, lecturers, and administrators. They have also excelled in various fields, producing notable scholars and academics like Prof. Grace Alele-Williams and Dr. Theresa Adebola.

Healthcare

In 2020, Women in Global Health Nigeria was established to bring visibility and recognition to Nigerian women shaping global health programming, policy, and advocacy in communities in Nigeria and the diaspora. Women have had a profound impact on healthcare and national development in several ways one of which is contributing to the healthcare workforce.

The likes of

- Dr. Maekeke, a female doctor who established the first maternity hospital in Nigeria
- Dora Akunyili former Director General NAFDAC. (Though, 2014)

Women for Health (W4H) in Nigeria has played a key role in the development of the health sector of the nation. The following are some of their programmes:

- i. Improving the capacity of colleges of nursing and midwifery and colleges of health technology to train female health workers, improving the accreditation status and training capacity of health training colleges, and increasing graduation rates.
- ii. Improving the recruitment, deployment, and retention of midwives in rural facilities while implementing a Foundation Year Training Programme, or access course, for rural women to improve their academic credentials, study skills, and confidence to enter health worker training.
- iii. Engaging with community, religious, and training institutions to create a gender-friendly environment for women to pursue health careers, and facilitating locally led scale-up.
- iv. Institutionalising short-term courses and modules in the curriculum to prepare health workers for deployment in conflict settings and humanitarian programming.

- v. Strengthened management systems and structures of 25 health training institutions.
- vi. Helped 14 schools receive full accreditation and 11 to achieve provisional accreditation.
- vii. Constructed 35 houses to accommodate midwives to support retention in rural areas.
- viii. Enabled 8,792 female students to enrol in midwifery, nursing, and community health extension worker training, with 38 per cent of the 1,551 graduates to date employed and working in rural facilities, a 134 per cent increase compared to the start of the program in 2012.
- ix. Enabled 2,818 rural female students to enrol in an access course and sponsorship initiative to achieve the qualifications needed to enter professional health training.
- x. Increased by more than 6,000 the number of students in training. (dai.com, 2024)

CONCLUSION

The concept of Women and gender have dominated both international and national discourses following the global realization of the fact that the capabilities of women have not been effectively harnessed for the development of the society, globally. In Nigeria, gender stereotypes have hindered women's contribution to national development, but over the years, the office of the First Lady though a ceremonial position, has evolved into a veritable platform for the promotion of social causes, support for women's empowerment and engagement in charitable activities above all a strong voice for gender advocacy. Women have been at the forefront of activism and advocacy for gender equity, equality, and women empowerment for national development. Despite challenges bordering on gender discrimination and stereotypes, women have also made significant contributions to national development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Although a lot needs to be done, it is believed that with continued advocacy on gender equity and equality, women will through leadership, political participation, professionalism, cultural inclusion, etc create a more significant impact on national development considering their population, strength, skill and their strategic role in the socialization process in the Nigerian state.

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